

The Customer Relationship Marketing in Insurance Sector

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Introduction

Relationship marketing is the process of building long term mutually beneficial relationship with customers. The service sectors in the developed countries are using this marketing tool very effectively by taking full advantage of information and communication technologies. Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) characterized by a ritual style of functioning till 1991 had to reinvent and strike a novel path for itself with the opening up of the economy. The organization has begun to think of measures to attract more and more new customer, while moving heaven and earth to retain the existing customers. To – day , LIC of India faces unique challenges to sustain their growth path for survival. The challenges include customer retention, reduction of transaction costs, risk management and regulation compliance. The industry is aware of the vital needs for evolving new strategies.

Evolution of Customer Relationship Marketing

One of the important marketing tools in the developed countries in relationship marketing. The Customer Relationship Marketing (CRM) is a comprehensive approach for creating, maintaining and expanding beneficial relationship with the customers.

The concept of CRM is vital to the insurance sector. Good customer service is the best brand ambassador for any mode of insurance. The entire business process consists of highly integrated efforts to discover, create, arouse and satisfy customers need.

Effectiveness of CRM in the Insurance Sector

Integration of policy administration system and CRM implementation would be useful for understanding the front office process management.

Customer – Centric Approach

The element of focus is the end-customer, not policies. The CRM implementations need to associate all the relevant information, including owned policies to the customer.

Strategy Enabling

The CRM architecture would help in perpetually evolving the business functionality and implementing digital innovation to support key strategies. Business and CRM should work in incrementally provide added value without undertaking lengthy and costly projects for every change.

Need for the Study

LIC Of India should provide quality service in tune with the customers expectations. They should respond to the requirements of the customers faster than their competitors. LIC of India must focus constant attention on the competitors performance, their strategy and style of operations and compare the same with its own performance, since customers always make this comparison before reaching decision.

Statement of the Roblem

Insurance industry occupies the centre stage in a fact developing country. All services in the insurance sector can be managed theoretically by information technology applications and the internet facility. LIC of India has come out with innovative measured to satisfy the needs of both the present and the potential customers and at the same time has initiated procedures and modalities to win back the lost customers. The philosophy and practices of CRM merit due consideration in the revival plan. The present study proposes to examine the CRM issues in Life Insurance Corporation of India.

Scope of the Study

The study has been undertaken mainly to highlight the customer relationship management with Life Insurance Corporation of India in Indigo District. This study is extremely useful to reach scholars to gain knowledge in customer relationship management. It helps the practicing manager to know about the trends in marketing scenario for arriving at better decisions. Based on the components identified, the relative importance of the insurance industry with that of the competitors is measured.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the demographic profile and awareness levels of the respondents in dindigul dist.
- To examine the conceptual framework of CRM in Life Insurance Corporation of India in the study area.
- To analyse the CRM practices implemented by the Life Insurance Corporation of India in the study area.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no significant difference between the policyholders with different age groups, educational level, occupational status, size of the family and different monthly income level relating to their perception about service quality in Life Insurance Corporation of India of the study area.
- There is no significant difference between the favourable and the unfavourable opinion of policyholders about customer retention in LIC of India.
- There is no significant difference between each segment.

Limitations of the Study

- The study depicts the present scenario of LIC of India in dindigul district and hence the result may not be applicable to another period of time or any other place.
- The study has no considered other life insurance companies, as LIC of India is the dominant player of the insurance in the dindigul district.
- Some respondents were neither motivated nor interested in expressing their perception about CRM in LIC in India.

Operational Definition of Concepts

Agent

An insurance company representative licensed by the state, who solicits, negotiate or effects contracts of insurance, and provides service to the policyholder for the insurer.

Assurance

Assurance is the coverage of risk on the happening of an event, which will happen during the period of insurance.

Bank Office

An office in which the administrative work of the business is carried out.

Bank Assurance

The relationship between a bank and an insurance company whereby the insurance company uses the bank sales channel in order to sell insurance products.

Brand Loyalty

The tendency of consumer to continue buying the same brand of goods rather than competing brands.

Claims

A claims is the demand that the insurer should redeem the promise made in the contract.

Cross Selling

The practice of selling an additional product or service to an existing customer.

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty is all about attracting the right customer, getting them to buy often buy in larger quantities and bring even more customers.

Conclusion

Insurance company as an industry that needs to contact customers frequently should pay more attention to customer relationship. The existing problems in the implementation of company CRM are obvious, so more and more insurance companies have realized the importance of customer relationship, but a perfect establishment of CRM also needs long – term efforts. The result of research for the implementation of insurances CRM showed that insurance's CRM is not professional desired results. It is used to spread information to send product information and to correspond with customers regarding their inquiries.